

<https://sobraj.com/index.php/yjhs>

Obstructive Nephropathy as the First Presentation for Breast Cancer: Case Report

Malik Ayaad ¹

¹ Department of Urology Unit Special Surgery, Faculty of Medicine, Mutah University Karak, Jordan.

Correspondence to:
Malik Ayaad
Email:
mkhadoop@yahoo.com

Abstract

In a rare occurrence, a case of breast cancer was initially detected with ureteral metastases. A biopsy performed through ureteroscopy confirmed the presence of carcinomatous cells. Subsequently, a mammogram revealed bilateral speculated mass lesions in the breasts. To obtain more definitive information, bilateral true-cut breast biopsies were conducted, and the histopathology analysis revealed invasive lobular carcinoma.

Keywords: *Obstructive Nephropathy, Breast Cancer, Case Report*

Citation: Ayaad, M. (2024). Obstructive nephropathy as the first presentation for breast cancer: Case report. Yaloo Journal for Health Sciences (YJHS), 1(1):1-4

Introduction

Breast cancer is a widely recognized malignancy that primarily affects women, with approximately 1.5 million new cases being diagnosed worldwide each year (Chahin et al., 2020; FS, 1999; Gabsi et al., 2018). Following surgical interventions, around 12% of breast cancer patients experience metastatic disease, commonly spreading to sites such as the lungs, spinal cord, bones, liver, and brain. In some cases, metastases may also occur in less common sites like the uterus, pituitary gland, ovaries, stomach, spleen, and kidneys (Zhou et al., 2019). However, metastasis to the ureters is a particularly rare occurrence, as reported in limited cases (Chahin et al., 2020; Chen et al., n.d.; FS, 1999; López-Martínez et al., 1996; Zhou et al., 2019). This paper presents a unique case involving bilateral obstructive hydronephrosis caused by obstructing masses in the ureters, later identified as metastatic breast cancer after a thorough diagnostic workup.

Chief Complaints:

A 48-year-old Jordanian female presented to the Department of Urology at a public hospital via the emergency room with complaints of no urine output for

24 hours, elevated creatinine levels, and bilateral hydronephrosis.

History of Present Illness:

One week prior to admission, the patient experienced a progressive decrease in urine output, lower limb swelling, generalized tiredness, mild bilateral flank pain, and vomiting.

On the day of admission, she reported no urine output for 24 hours. Laboratory tests revealed a serum creatinine level of 4.5 mg/dl and a potassium level of 6.1 mmol/L. A computed tomography (CT) scan without contrast was performed, which showed bilateral hydronephrosis and bilateral ureteral dilatation down to the mid-ureter, with suspicious soft tissue masses identified. (See Figure 1)

Figure 1

Personal and Family History:

The patient had no personal history of renal disorders or chronic diseases. However, she reported a family history of ovarian cancer and thyroid cancer among second-degree relatives.

Management:

Upon stabilization by the nephrology team, the patient underwent bilateral double J insertion. The serum creatinine level decreased to 1.7 mg/dl initially. However, two days later, she experienced no urine output, and the serum creatinine started to rise again despite the double J stents being in place.

Subsequently, bilateral double J removal with bilateral ureteroscopy (URS) was performed. During the URS, luminal soft tissue projections were observed at the mid-ureter bilaterally, and biopsies were taken. New bilateral double J stents were inserted. The biopsy results revealed the presence of carcinomatous cells, and immunostaining showed positivity for estrogen receptors and progesterone receptors. A pelvic MRI was conducted, which demonstrated multiple bony metastases.

Further Evaluation:

Thorough history taking and physical examination were conducted. The patient denied any previous complaints, and the breast examination was normal. A mammogram was performed, revealing bilateral speculated mass lesions (See Figure 2).

Figure 2

Bilateral true-cut breast biopsies were performed, and the histopathology confirmed the diagnosis of invasive lobular carcinoma. Immunostaining showed positivity for estrogen receptors (100%), progesterone receptors (100%), and ki67 (50%). HER2neu, CK5/6, and E-Cadherin were negative. As the serum creatinine failed to decrease below 1.6 mg/dl, both double J stents were removed and replaced with bilateral nephrostomy tubes, allowing for further staging workup. The patient was subsequently transferred to an oncology center, where she initiated hormonal therapy.

Literature Review and Discussion

Ureteral metastasis of breast cancer is an extremely rare occurrence (FS, 1999; López-Martínez et al., 1996). Studies have shown that ureteral metastasis accounts for only a small percentage, approximately 7.8%, of all cases of ureteral metastasis, with the more common causes being stomach, prostate, and bladder cancers (FS, 1999; Haddad et al., 1999).

While there have been reports discussing the incidence of ureteral metastasis in patients with breast cancer, most of these cases were identified after the patients had already been diagnosed with breast cancer (Chahin et al., 2020; FS, 1999; Gabsi et al., 2018). In our case, we present a unique scenario where ureteral metastasis was the initial presentation of breast cancer.

Approximately 36% of patients with ureteral metastasis exhibit no specific systemic symptoms such as lumbar pain, nausea, weight loss, or urinary tract infection (Rigondet et al., 1988; Zhou et al., 2019). Many cases are asymptomatic, and hematuria is not commonly observed since ureteral metastasis tends to invade from the outside or occur beneath the mucosa (ZHANG et al., 2016). In our case, the patient experienced a one-week history of progressive decrease in urine output, lower limb swelling, generalized tiredness, mild bilateral flank pain, and vomiting, without any reported hematuria.

Distinguishing between metastatic ureteral tumors and ureteral urothelial carcinoma can be challenging, but the patient's clinical history can provide important clues, particularly if the patient has a known history of cancer, which was not the case in our patient (Zhou et al., 2019). Imaging studies may offer limited assistance, especially when the tumor does not adhere to the mucosa (Presman & Ehrlich, 1948).

Several characteristics of metastatic ureteral cancers have been reported, including the presence of tumor cells in the ureteral wall or in the vessels and lymph nodes surrounding the ureter (Presman & Ehrlich, 1948). A definitive diagnosis can be achieved through biopsy performed via ureteroscopy. However, limited sample sizes often pose a challenge in providing a clear pathological diagnosis. In cases where ureteroscopy does not yield a conclusive diagnosis, exploratory laparotomy is recommended (Zhou et al., 2019). In our case, the biopsy conducted during ureteroscopy revealed the presence of carcinomatous cells with positivity for estrogen and progesterone receptors.

Although metastatic breast cancers are generally not curable, treatment options such as surgical resection of isolated metastatic lesions, combined with systemic treatment and radiotherapy targeting the postsurgical

tumor sites, have shown effectiveness (Lin et al., 2013; Sharma et al., 2010). Systemic treatment is typically tailored based on the primary tumor and metastatic sites (Sharma et al., 2010; Zhou et al., 2019). Chemotherapy, molecular-targeted therapy, hormonal therapy, immunotherapy, nanotechnology, and gene therapy are examples of systemic treatments, with chemotherapy being the most commonly employed (Amar et al., 2009; Ayyad et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2019). The median survival for patients with metastatic breast cancer ranges from 24 to 30 months. The prognosis is largely determined by the site and extent of organ involvement (Ayyad et al., 2023, 2023; Nicolini et al., 2006).

Conclusion

In cases of rare breast cancer presenting with ureteral metastases, an important initial step in the diagnostic process is the performance of an adequate biopsy through ureteroscopy. This approach becomes particularly crucial when the patient has no previous history of breast cancer and lacks specific symptoms. Histopathological examination and immunohistochemistry play a pivotal role in achieving an accurate clinical diagnosis. By analyzing the tissue samples obtained through ureteroscopy, healthcare professionals can gain valuable insights into the nature and characteristics of metastatic breast cancer, aiding in treatment planning and management decisions.

References

- Ayyad, M., Ayaad, O., Alkhatatbeh, H., Sawaqed, F., Al-Rawashdeh, S., & Qaddumi, B. (2023). The effectiveness of gabapentin in treating overactive bladder: a quasi-experimental study. *Immunopathologia Persa*, 10(1), e40574-e40574.
- Ayyad, M., Ayaad, O., Alkhatatbeh, H., Sawaqed, F., & Al-Rawashdah, S. (2022). Laparoscopic partial nephrectomy: off-clamp versus on clamp. *Asian Pacific Journal of Cancer Prevention: APJCP*, 23(5), 1719. Amar, S., Roy, V., & Perez, E. A. (2009). Treatment of metastatic breast cancer: Looking towards the future. In *Breast Cancer Research and Treatment* (Vol. 114, Issue 3, pp. 413–422). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10549-008-0032-3>
- Chahin, M., Chhatrala, H., Krishnan, N., Brow, D., & Zuberi, L. (2020). Triple-Negative Lobular Breast Cancer Causing Hydronephrosis. *Journal of Investigative Medicine High Impact Case Reports*, 8, 232470962090595. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2324709620905954>
- Chen, Y., Wu, J., & Wang, J. (n.d.). Male Breast Cancer with Ureteral Metastasis: a case report. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-37173/v1>
- FS, H. (1999). Metastases to the ureter. Review of the world literature, and three new case reports - *PubMed*. 47(4), 265–271. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/10641458/>
- Gabsi, A., Yahiaoui, Y., Zenhani, A., Herbegue, K., Meddeb, K., Mokrani, A., Letaief, F., Ayadi, M., Rais, H., Chraiet, N., Haouet, S., & Mezlini, A. (2018). Ureteral metastasis in carcinoma of the breast. *Urology Case Reports*, 21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eucr.2018.08.012>
- Lin, N. U., Thomssen, C., Cardoso, F., Cameron, D., Cufer, T., Fallowfield, L., Francis, P. A., Kyriakides, S., Pagani, O., Senkus, E., Costa, A., & Winer, E. P. (2013). International guidelines for management of metastatic breast cancer (MBC) from the European School of Oncology (ESO)-MBC Task Force: Surveillance, staging, and evaluation of patients with early-stage and metastatic breast cancer. In *Breast* (Vol. 22, Issue 3, pp. 203–210). Churchill Livingstone. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.breast.2013.03.006>
- López-Martínez, R. A., Stock, J. A., Gump, F. E., & Rosen, J. S. (1996). Carcinoma of the breast metastatic to the ureter presenting with flank pain and recurrent urinary tract infection. *American Surgeon*, 62, 748–752.
- Nicolini, A., Giardino, R., Carpi, A., Ferrari, P., Anselmi, L., Colosimo, S., Conte, M., Fini, M., Giavaresi, G., Berti, P., & Miccoli, P. (2006). Metastatic breast cancer: an updating. *Biomedicine and Pharmacotherapy*, 60(9), 548–556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2006.07.086>
- Presman, D., & Ehrlich, L. (1948). Metastatic Tumors of the Ureter. *Journal of Urology*, 59(3), 312–325. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5347\(17\)69379-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-5347(17)69379-0)
- Rigondet, G., Salé, J., & Lautier, A. (1988). Secondary tumor of the ureter. Metastasis of breast carcinoma. *Annales d'urologie*, 22(4), 301. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/3190171>
- Sharma, G. N., Dave, R., Sanadya, J., Sharma, P., & Sharma, K. K. (2010). Various types and management of breast cancer: An overview. In *Journal of Advanced Pharmaceutical Technology and Research* (Vol. 1, Issue 2, pp. 109–126). Wolters Kluwer -- Medknow Publications. [/pmc/articles/PMC3255438/?report=abstract](https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/2324709620905954/)
- ZHANG, D., LI, H., & GAN, W. (2016). Hydronephrosis associated with ureteral metastasis of prostate cancer: A rare case report. *Molecular and Clinical Oncology*, 4(4), 597–598. <https://doi.org/10.3892/mco.2016.775>
- Zhou, Z. H., Sun, L. J., & Zhang, G. M. (2019). Ureter - an unusual site of breast cancer metastasis: A case report. *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 7(20), 3347–3352. <https://doi.org/10.12998/wjcc.v7.i20.3347>

